

Relationship between Health, Happiness and Intergenerational Relationship among the Elderly Population

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Abstract:- The worldwide elderly population is on the rise, necessitating a shift in focus towards addressing the requirements of older individuals. The chains of relationship between generations are known as Intergenerational Relations. Due to the decreased birth rate, increased life expectancy and increased migration among family members for employment and education, the situation of older adults in the family become worse. They are more prone to loneliness, isolation and depression. The time spent together among the family members have been reduced in the present situation. Various studies have shown that the intergenerational solidarity can contribute to their positive mental health. Hence the current study aims to find the relationship between health status of an elderly, happiness and intergenerational relationship among the elderly. The study is a descriptive one. Simple Random Sampling is used. Self-structured interview schedule has been used to collect data. Based on the findings suggestions provided.

Keywords:- Elderly, Health, Happiness, Intergenerational Relationship.

I. INTRODUCTION

The world is witnessing an unprecedented demographic shift with a significant increase in the elderly population. This demographic transition presents both opportunities and challenges. Health and happiness are two fundamental dimensions of well-being, and they are inherently intertwined. An individual's health significantly impacts their overall sense of happiness and life satisfaction (Banjare, P., et al, 2015). Furthermore, intergenerational relationships hold a unique place in the lives of the elderly, offering emotional support, caregiving, and a sense of continuity. In urban slum (Chandanshive, P., et al, 2022) environments, the dynamics of these relationships may be altered due to the challenges posed by limited space, economic disparities, and cultural shifts. Exploring the nature of intergenerational ties among elderly urban slum dwellers is essential to grasp the broader sociocultural context in which they live and the impact of

these relationships on their well-being. This research endeavor seeks to shed light on the multifaceted relationship between health (Samanta, T., et al, 2015), happiness, and intergenerational interactions among elderly urban slum dwellers in Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu (Nancy, F. X. Lovelina Little Flower, 2021).

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

This study explores the influence mechanism of the elderly mental health. The mental health of the growing elderly population with happiness as a key dimension becomes a social issue and public health concern. However, this study results towards a positive predictive effect of happiness on mental health with meditating, income and satisfaction. Moreover, this study suggests to improve the multi-subjective mental health support service system to create public value and awareness on mental health with coping mechanism. Furthermore, this study understands the complex relationship between elderly and social levels resulting to provide empirical support for healthy ageing among elderly population for future policy making (Sun Y. 2023).

Happiness is a concept of subjective wellbeing or a form of satisfaction every person is willing to achieve. Happiness in the older person is the sum of his or her lifelong achievement. This study analysis the demographic, family, personal, social and health factors with the subjective perception of elderly happiness to improve their physical, mental and social health. However, this study results on explaining happiness through absence of depression and hopelessness with enhanced psychological wellbeing for a high quality of life. Moreover this study suggests for possible factors that enhances public policy, educational programs, community empowerment etc. furthermore, these aspects form an essential functions towards public, social and mental health in elderly population (Segura, A., et al. 2023)

This study determined the factors associates with the happiness in elderly population. However, this study results that the factors like income, social participation and

engagement, emotional support from children and grandchildren were associated with happiness and this study results towards high overall elderly happiness. Furthermore, this study ensures receiving social, emotional and family support, for elderly active and social engagement which enhances the elderly levels of overall happiness (Shah. S., et al, 2021)

This study aims to explore the levels of health and happiness in the elderly population. This study explores the relationship between using cross sectional analysis. However, this study results that low level of happiness was associated with the poverty, health and relationship. Thus, this study insist for an optimism approaches in enhancing the health and happiness within the elderly population (Anger. E., et al, 2009)

This study identifies the reverse intergenerational support which has created role conflicts within different age groups especially with the elderly population. This study results that the stop in economic support reduces the elderly level of happiness and decrease their health concerns and spiritual support improves the level of elderly happiness. Thus the reverse intergenerational support and the role conflict has an immense effect among the levels of overall elderly happiness and health. (Zhang. H., et al, 2023)

This study analysis the intergeneration relationship between the elderly and their subjective well-being with Chinese migrants. However, this study results towards a positive linkage with subjective wellbeing and self-related health issues connective with feeling of closeness and quality of life. Furthermore, this study identifies a strong sense of closeness with the children, quality of life and happiness leading towards emotional connection for a betterment of health and wellbeing. (Lai Daniel., et al, 2019)

➤ *Objectives of the Study*

This study aims to find the relationship between the level of Happiness, Intergenerational relationship and Health status of the elderly population living in urban slum.

III. METHODS AND MATERIALS

The study adopts descriptive research method (Siedlecki and Sandra, 2020) in which it extensively describes the health, intergenerational relationship and the level of happiness among the elderly residing in the urban slum of Coimbatore city. Geographically analyzing the Coimbatore City Municipal Corporation is divided into five zones namely North, South, Central, East and West. Each zone and has 20 wards. This city has a total of 319 pockets of slums with 46,650 households. The researcher on identifying the population density has collected data from Central Zone. There are about 24 slums and 4119 households in the central zone. Which is further classified into 6 tenable slums and 18 untenable slums. The tenability of the slums are identified by the condition of infrastructure facilities available, water supply, sanitation

facilities, etc. the vulnerability of the community people increases as the untenable situation increases. So the researcher wants to collect data from one of untenable slums. The researcher collected data from 58 respondents from Danalakshmi Nagar, a slum of central zone which has 254 households in Coimbatore Corporation using simple random sampling.

The tools used for data collection adopted interview schedule method which consists of three parts. The first part comprises the demographic profile of the respondents and health status. The second part of the interview schedule focuses on the intergenerational relationship as perceived by the respondents. The next part of the interview schedule focuses on the level of happiness among the respondents using The Oxford Happiness Questionnaire (Hills and Argyle, 2002) has been used to know the level of happiness among the respondents. The collected data has been analyzed through SPSS version 2021 with appropriate statistical test.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Half of the respondents belongs to the age group of 60-70 years of age, 39.7% of the respondents belongs to the age group of 70-80 years of age. 65.5% of the respondents are female and 34.5% of the respondents are male. Majority of the respondents belong to SC/ST Community and 17.2% of the respondents belong to BC Community. A vast majority of the respondents (86.2%) are Hindus and 10.3% of the respondents are Christians. Majority of the respondents (69%) live with their spouse and above 1/4th of the respondents (27.6%) are widowed. 62.1% of the respondents live with their spouse, son and their family, 17.2% of the respondents lives without spouse, son and family and the other 17.2% of the respondents lives without spouse and daughter and family. Only 3.4% of the respondents live with their spouse, daughter and family. Above half of the respondents (55.2%) depend on their spouse, nearly 1/4th of the respondents (24.1%) depend on their daughter, 17.2% depend on their son. 43.1% of the respondents perceive that the Intergenerational relationship with the other generations in the family is low, 29.3% of the respondents perceive as high and 27.6% of the respondents perceive it as moderate. 39.7% of the respondents level of happiness is moderate, 34.5% of the respondents have high level of happiness and 1/4th of the respondents have low level of happiness. 34.5% of the respondents rate their health status as moderate, another 34.5% of the respondents rate their health status as high and the other 31% of the respondents rate their health status as low.

The results further relatively pinpoints that about 44.8% of the respondents perceive that feeling of closeness with their intergenerational family members (Khanlary Z., et al, 2016) are sometimes close, 34.5% of the respondents feel it as not close. 44.8% of the respondents perceive that sharing leisure time activities by their intergenerational family members is less frequent and 27.6% of the respondents share leisure time

activities sometimes. 37.9% of the respondents perceive that face to face contact (Bagshaw D, et al, 2015) between the family members is frequent and 31% of the respondents

perceive that it is less frequent. 37.9% of the respondents perceive that sharing the household chores sometimes happens and 31% respond that it happens rarely.

Table 1 Correlation Analysis of Elderly Health, Happiness and Intergenerational Relationship

Correlations		Intergenerational Relationship	Level of Happiness	Rating of Health Status
Inter-generational Relationship	Pearson Correlation	1	.470**	.591**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000
	N	58	58	58
Level of Happiness	Pearson Correlation	.470**	1	.824**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000
	N	58	58	58
Rating of Health Status	Pearson Correlation	.591**	.824**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	
	N	58	58	58

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The above table shows that Pearson Correlations test has been used to find out the relationship between Intergenerational Relationship, Level of Happiness and Rating of Health Status. The analysis clearly denoted the Intergenerational Relationship correlate with level of happiness $r (.470^{**})$, $p < .0.01$ and Rating of Health Status $r (.591^{**})$, $p < .0.01$. The analysis clearly denoted that the Level of Happiness correlate with of Health Status $r (.824^{**})$, $p < .0.01$. Thus it can be inferred that there exist a high relationship and interconnection between all the three variables in the study.

V. SUGGESTIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Since it is found that there is a correlation between Intergenerational Relationship, Level of Happiness and Rating of Health Status, intergenerational programs and activities which encourage closer relationships and interactions (Livingston G., et al, 2013) among family members from different generations shall be promoted. These programs can include storytelling sessions, shared hobbies, or collaborative community projects (Murayama, Y., et al, 2015). A significant proportion of respondents (31%) have perceived low levels of happiness and health, it's essential to provide mental health support services in slums (Barua, K., et al, 2017). Awareness shall be provided about mental health and offer counseling services to help elderly individuals cope with loneliness, stress, and other emotional challenges (Sakurai, R., et al, 2016). Community-based initiatives that promote physical and social activities for the elderly shall be facilitated. These initiatives can include exercise classes, hobby clubs, and support groups, (Deborah Parkinson & Judith Turner, 2019) which can positively impact both happiness and health. Family members shall be encouraged to actively engage with their elderly parents and grandparents.

VI. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the study aimed to find the relationship between the health, happiness, and intergenerational relationships among the elderly. The analysis using Pearson Correlations demonstrated significant relationships between these dimensions. Notably, intergenerational relationships were positively correlated with both happiness and health status. Moreover, happiness exhibited a strong positive correlation with health status. These findings underscore the interconnectedness of these factors in shaping the well-being of elderly urban slum dwellers. By implementing the recommended strategies and interventions, one can contribute to enhancing the quality of life and well-being of this often marginalized demographic, fostering a more inclusive and supportive environment for elderly individuals.

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